

THERMALLY CONDUCTIVE CARBON FILLED POLYMER COMPOSITES

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1. Introduction

According to demands of thermal conductive materials, thermal conductivity of polymeric hybrid materials becomes increasingly important for electronic packaging and semiconductor chips because their heat dissipation ability limits the reliability, performance, and miniaturization of advanced electronic circuits [1-4]. Most polymers are thermally-insulating materials but they can be used for other applications if their properties are modified. Typical thermal conductivity values for some common materials are 0.1 to 0.3 W/m.K for polymers, 230 W/m.K for aluminum, 400 W/m.K for copper and 600 W/m.K for graphite. Using these thermally conductive fillers, resulting polymer composites show sufficient levels of thermal conductivity to fulfill the requirements for certain applications with maintaining the advantages of polymers in terms of weight reduction, design flexibility, durability and manufacturing cost reduction [5, 6].

One approach to improving thermal conductivity of a polymer is the addition of conductive fillers such as graphite powder, carbon nanotube, carbon fibers and graphene. Several research studies have been conducted to improve the thermal conductivity of the polymeric composites. Various fillers have been used to improve the thermal conductivity of the resulting polymer composite materials. Kakaitzidou *et al.* [7] have demonstrated the use of expanded graphite platelets to enhance the thermal conductivity and mechanical properties of polymeric resins. Debelak *et al.* [8] showed a 24-fold increase in thermal conductivity for the 20 wt% graphite flake containing composite compared to pure epoxy resin. Ma *et al.* [9] indicated that grafting silane molecules onto a nanotube surface improved dispersion of the nanotubes in the epoxy matrix, thereby improving the thermal conductivity. Other

strategies to obtain higher thermal conductivities involve aligning the anisotropic fillers in the direction of heat flow and the use of a mixture of filler materials of different sizes and shapes [10]. Kuriger *et al.* [11] founded that the thermal conductivity of the polypropylene/ carbon fiber composites in the direction parallel to the fiber alignment was much larger than that normal to it. Similar enhanced thermal conductivities are reported for the polymer/carbon fiber composites based on polyimide [12], and polyamides [13]. Concerning the filler sizes and shape, Kim *et al.* [14] used a mixture of micro-sized carbon fibers and multi-walled carbon nanotubes to make phenolic resin nanocomposites and showed the increased thermal conductivity.

In this work, we explored the thermal conductivity and mechanical property changes upon the incorporation of hybrid carbon fillers into polyamide 6. In other words, this study investigates the property changes from two fillers of very different shape: graphite with flake and sheet shape and carbon fiber with rod type filler. Filler alignment was achieved by injection molding process.

2. Experimental section

2.1 Materials

A commercial grade of polyamide 6, *i.e.*, EN 300 (PA 6) supplied by KP Chemtech., was chosen that is commonly used for injection molding and extrusion applications. Synthetic graphite (GR) that is available from Showa Denko Carbon Inc., was used due to its high thermal conductivity and high electrical conductivity. Two different carbon fillers were employed in this work. Polyacrylonitrile (PAN) based carbon fiber is bundle type (b-CF, aspect ratio : 100~200) while pitch based carbon fiber from Cytec Co., was monofilament type (m-CF, aspect ratio :

20). Both carbon fibers and graphite were used as conductive fillers.

2.2 Melt Processing

Prior to melt processing, the PA 6 and the carbon fillers were dried for a minimum of 24 h in a vacuum oven at 80°C. Composites were melt compounded in a co-rotating twin screw extruder using a barrel temperature of 260-290°C, a screw speed of 180 rpm, and a feed rate of 1 kg/h. The PA 6 and two carbon fillers were dry-blended prior to extrusion and introduced into the extruder by a single hopper. Tensile specimens (ASTM D638, Type I) and Izod bars (ASTM D256) were prepared by an injection-molding machine using a barrel temperature of 270 (feed) to 290°C (die). After molding, the samples were immediately sealed in a polyethylene bag and placed in a vacuum desiccator for a minimum of 24 h prior to testing.

2.3 Characterization

The thermal conductivity, κ , is defined as following equation (1),

$$\kappa = \alpha \cdot c_p \cdot \rho \quad (1)$$

where α is thermal diffusivity, c_p is specific heat, and ρ is density. The thermal diffusivity is defined as following relationship (2),

$$\alpha = 1.38 \cdot L^2 / \pi^2 \cdot t_{1/2} \quad (2)$$

where L is the thickness of the specimen and t is time. The thermal conductivity is estimated based on laser flash method using Netzsch LFA 447. The specific heat and density of the specimen are determined with modulated differential scanning calorimeter and gas pycnometer, respectively.

Samples for morphology analysis were taken from the central region of an Izod bar. The central sample region was located parallel and perpendicular to the flow direction *ca.* 3-4 cm away from the far end of a 12.8 cm Izod bar and half-way between the top and bottom surfaces of the bar. Sections taken from the core region of injection-molded specimens were viewed parallel to the two orthogonal axes, flow direction (FD), and transverse direction (TD). This nomenclature has been used elsewhere [15-17]. Smooth surface was obtained by

polishing molded bars. Polishing was accomplished using a series of successively finer abrasives. The final polishing steps made use of a 6 μm diamond paste followed by 0.05 μm alumina. In what follows, optical microscopy analyses were made on a view observed parallel to the transverse direction, or TD (FD–ND plane) and viewed parallel to the flow direction, or FD (TD–ND plane), as shown in Figure 1.

Stress-strain analyses were performed at room temperature according to ASTM D638 using an Instron testing machine upgraded for computerized data acquisition. Values of the tensile modulus were determined using an extensometer at a cross-head rate of 0.51 cm/min. Izod impact tests were conducted using a 6.8 J hammer and 3.5 m/s impact velocity at room temperature using an Impact tester. Standard notches were made according to ASTM D256. Typically, data from at least five specimens were averaged to determine mechanical properties. Thermal expansion tests were conducted according to ASTM D696 using a thermomechanical analyzer (TMA, TA instrument). Rectangular specimens were prepared by milling the center part of injection-molded Izod bars (as-molded) to the following dimensions: 3.175 mm thickness, 6.35 mm width, and 12.7 mm height. To investigate the directional dependence of thermal expansion, measurements were made in the three orthogonal directions, *i.e.*, FD, TD, and ND, as depicted in Figure 1. In order to examine the effect of the thermal history, specimens were annealed at 150 °C for 8 h in a vacuum oven. Thermal expansion tests were performed over the temperature range from -10 to 150 °C at the rate of 5 °C /min in a nitrogen atmosphere.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Morphology

Figure 2 shows the optical microscope photographs of PA 6/Graphite/Carbon fiber composites. For both cases of different carbon fibers, b-CF and m-CF, the carbon fibers are generally well-dispersed in PA 6 matrix. These photographs also reveal that the fibers are oriented in the mold fill direction as expected.

3.2 Mechanical properties

The modulus and Izod impact strength of PA 6/Graphite/b-CF (or m-CF) composites are shown in Figure 3 versus the filler content. For both series of

composites, there is a substantial increase in stiffness over the entire range of filler contents. Because most of graphites and carbon fibers are well-dispersed in the PA 6 phase as demonstrated in Figure 2, the PA 6 matrix is efficiently reinforced by the fillers. The notched Izod impact strength for these composites is also shown in Figure 3. There is a very large difference in impact strength for the composites of PA 6/Graphite/b-CF versus PA 6/Graphite/m-CF. The PA 6/Graphite/m-CF composite fails in a brittle manner in this test while the PA 6/Graphite/b-CF composite is quite tough. This level of toughness for the latter can be attributed to the high aspect ratio of b-CF compared to m-CF.

3.3 Thermal conductivity

The composite materials used in this work show the high anisotropy owing to high anisotropic carbon fibers. As a result, there is a huge difference in properties including the thermal conductivity. Figure 4 shows the in-plane and through-plane thermal conductivity results for the composites containing various amounts of multiple carbon fillers, graphite and carbon fiber, as a function of weight fraction. In-plane and through-plane thermal conductivities refer to the thermal conductivities of ① and ② directions, respectively. For both series of composites, there is an increase in thermal conductivity over the entire range of filler contents. And in-plane thermal conductivity is always higher than through-plane thermal conductivity due to the high anisotropy of fillers. Figure 5 shows the thermographic images of the composites. After 300 seconds, highly filled composites show definite color changes indicating the efficient heat transfer. It shows a good agreement with thermal conductivity result that is shown in Figure 4.

3.3 Linear thermal expansion behavior

The linear thermal expansion behavior of the composite was recorded over a broad temperature range; however, over the entire temperature range of interest, e.g. -10 to 150°C, the linear thermal expansion coefficients, or CTEs cannot be represented by a single value. Therefore, we selected the following ranges: 0-30, and 80-100°C. Figure 6 show the CTE values measured in all directions for PA 6/Graphite/m-CF composites as a function of filler contents. As expected, the CTE along the FD and the TD decreases dramatically as filler content

increases; whereas, the CTE along the ND shows only small decrease as filler content increases. The addition of carbon fillers causes significant reductions in CTE for the FD and TD.

Fig.1. Schematic diagram of the sampling for thermal conductivity and thermal expansion measurement.

Fig.2. Optical microscope photographs of PA 6/Graphite/Carbon fiber composites observed along (a) and (c) the flow direction and (b) and (d) transverse direction. (a) and (b) for the composites based on b-CF and (c) and (d) for those based on m-CF.

(a)

(b)

Fig.3. Tensile modulus and Izod impact strength of the PA 6/Graphite/Carbon fiber composites based on (a) b-CF and (b) m-CF.

(a)

(b)

Fig.4. Thermal conductivity of the PA 6/Graphite/Carbon fiber composites based on (a) b-CF and (b) m-CF.

Fig.5. Thermography of the specimens for the PA 6/Graphite/Carbon fiber composites based on (a)~(d) b-CF and (e)~(g) m-CF. Specimen (a) and (e) are neat PA 6. Specimen (b), (c) and (d) are PA/Graphite/b-CF composites with volume ratio of 80:8:12, 67:6:27 and 64:8:28, respectively. And specimen (f) and (g) are PA/Graphite/m-CF composites with volume ratio of 70:20:10 and 56:22:22, respectively. Hot plate temperature is set at 100°C.

Fig.6. Linear thermal expansion coefficient for the PA 6/Graphite/m-CF composites with measuring temperature range of (a) 0~30 °C and (b) 60~80 °C.

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